
**ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF INVESTMENT
ACCOUNTING ON THE FORMATION OF
PRODUCTION COSTS****Abdunazarov Jasurbek Abdurakhmonovich**

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ABSTRACT

This thesis highlights the impact of correctly organizing inventory accounting at enterprises on the formation of production costs. Inventories are the primary material resource of the enterprise's production process, and their correct accounting ensures the reliability of production costs, financial results, and profit indicators. The thesis analyzes the relationship between the movement of inventories, their valuation, consumption rates, material costs, and cost formation.

Introduction. In a market economy, the efficiency of enterprise activities depends, first and foremost, on the level of rational use of production resources. In particular, in manufacturing enterprises, inventories serve as an important economic resource, ensuring the continuity of the production process. Raw materials, materials, fuel, spare parts, semi-finished products, and other inventories constitute the bulk of production costs.

Proper accounting of inventories is essential for determining enterprise expenses, calculating production costs, evaluating financial results, and making management decisions. If inventories are assessed incorrectly or their consumption is not accurately reflected in the accounting, production costs will also be formed incorrectly. This may negatively affect the company's profit, profitability, and tax base indicators.

Main part. Inventories occupy a special place in the structure of production costs. This is because the raw materials and supplies consumed during the production process are directly included in the cost of production. Therefore, it is necessary to establish effective control over the receipt, storage, production, and write-off of reserves.

The impact of inventory accounting on production costs is manifested in several directions. Firstly, the correct assessment of inventories ensures the accurate formation of production costs. The acquisition cost of materials, transportation and procurement costs, customs duties, and other direct costs affect the value of inventories. If these costs are accounted for incorrectly, the cost of the product may be artificially increased or decreased.

Second, accounting for material consumption strengthens control over production costs. The established consumption rates for each type of product must be compared with the actual consumption. Excessive consumption can be associated with production losses, technological defects, poor control, or low material quality.

Thirdly, inventory turnover indicates the efficiency of the enterprise's use of working capital. The accumulation of excess inventory in the warehouse causes funds to be left out of

the production process. This negatively affects the liquidity and financial stability of the enterprise.

Fourthly, accounting data on inventories are an important source of information when making management decisions. Based on this information, management determines which types of materials are consumed more, which products have higher production costs, and in which areas costs can be reduced.

The share of material costs in the formation of production costs can be determined by the following formula:

$$MXU = (MX / IX) \times 100$$

Where: MCO is the share of material costs; MX — amount of material costs; IX — total production costs. This indicator allows for the determination of the share of material resources in the cost of production. If the share of material costs is high, it will be necessary to conduct a deep analysis of the efficiency of material utilization at the enterprise.

The material capacity indicator is also of great importance:

$$MS = MX / Q$$

Here: MS is the material capacity; MX — material costs; Q is the volume of production. An increase in material intensity means that more material is consumed per unit of output. This situation is a negative indicator for the enterprise and leads to an increase in production costs.

The influence of inventory accounting on cost formation can be expressed through the following analytical directions:

Analysis direction	Credentials	Economic result
Assessment of inventories	Purchase cost, transport and procurement expenses	Clear formation of production costs
Material consumption control	Consumption norms and actual consumption indicators	Identify excess costs
Analysis of storage balances	Incoming, outgoing, and remaining data	Effective use of working capital
Analytical accounting	Information broken down by material type, workshop, product, and responsible person	Justification of management decisions

The correct organization of analytical accounting is also important when maintaining inventory records. Maintaining inventory records by types of materials, warehouses, financially accountable persons, production units, and product types allows for an accurate analysis of costs. This helps to identify excessive costs and losses in a timely manner.

Today, the automation of accounting, electronic document management, and the use of barcode and QR code systems at enterprises allow for real-time monitoring of inventory movement. This makes the process of forming production costs more transparent and precise.

Conclusion. Maintaining proper inventory accounting directly influences the formation of production costs. Assessing inventories, accurately accounting for their inflow and outflow,

and controlling material consumption based on standards ensure the reliable formation of production costs.

Analysis shows that to reduce production costs at enterprises, it is necessary to further improve inventory accounting, strengthen analytical accounting, regularly revise material consumption standards, and implement digital accounting systems. Thus, inventory accounting is not only a tool for maintaining accounting records but also an important economic mechanism for managing production costs, reducing costs, and increasing the financial efficiency of an enterprise.

Suggestions

- Analytical accounting for inventories at enterprises must be maintained by type of material and production units.
- It is necessary to regularly compare planned and actual material consumption indicators.
- A separate control system should be established for excess and slow-moving inventories in warehouses.
- It is advisable to account for the movement of inventories through automated programs.

Material consumption standards must be revised on a scientific basis to reduce production costs.

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